

ASSESSING DAYLIGHTING STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING USER COMFORT IN THE PROPOSED PRIME UNIVERSITY SENATE BUILDING, ABUJA, NIGERIA: A SIMULATION-BASED APPROACH

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Abstract: *This study assessed the effectiveness of daylighting strategies for enhancing user comfort in the proposed Prime University Senate Building, Abuja, Nigeria, using a simulation-based approach. The study examined the influence of architectural design variables, including building orientation, courtyard configuration, window placement, facade treatments, and roof-level daylight openings on indoor daylight performance. A design-based research methodology integrating literature review, architectural design exploration, and daylight simulation using Sefaira was adopted. Daylight Factor (DF) served as the primary performance indicator for evaluating daylight availability across six floor levels. Results showed that spaces adjacent to courtyards and external façades achieved higher daylight factor values, while deep-plan areas such as the auditorium exhibited lower daylight penetration. Daylight performance improved progressively on the upper floors due to increased sky exposure and reduced external obstruction. The findings demonstrate that courtyard integration, optimized fenestration, and climate-responsive design strategies significantly enhance daylight distribution and visual comfort while reducing dependence on artificial lighting. The study concludes that simulation-driven daylighting assessment provides a reliable framework for improving environmental performance and occupant comfort in institutional buildings within tropical savannah climates.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Daylighting is a fundamental aspect of sustainable architectural design, enhancing visual comfort, indoor environmental quality, occupant well-being, and energy efficiency (Vásquez et al., 2022; Negarestan, 2025). Through the effective use of natural light, buildings can reduce reliance on artificial lighting and associated energy consumption. Strategies such as appropriate building orientation, optimized fenestration, courtyards, skylights, and shading devices have been identified as key measures for achieving environmentally responsive and user-centered buildings (Aslam et al., 2024).

According to the National Universities Commission (NUC) (2020), Abuja has experienced significant expansion in educational infrastructure over the past two decades, increasing the need for sustainable building solutions that respond to local climatic conditions. Given Abuja's high solar radiation levels, natural daylight presents a valuable resource for improving building performance and occupant comfort (Abubakar, 2014; Aliyu, 2016). However, maximizing daylight benefits requires careful design considerations to balance daylight availability, glare control, thermal comfort, and energy efficiency.

University senate buildings serve as major administrative centers housing offices, conference facilities, meeting rooms, and public service areas (Muhammed & Lateef, 2025). The

diverse functions performed within these spaces demand adequate visual comfort to support productivity and user satisfaction (Orewere et al., 2020; Orewere et al., 2024). Despite the growing interest in sustainable building design, studies investigating daylighting performance in university administrative buildings within the Nigerian context remain limited, particularly those employing simulation-based evaluation methods during the design stage.

Although previous research has demonstrated the positive influence of daylighting strategies on occupant comfort and building performance (Madan et al., 2024; Tabadkani et al., 2021), there is a paucity of studies focusing on large university administrative buildings in Abuja's tropical savannah climate. To address this gap, this study evaluates the effectiveness of daylighting strategies in enhancing user comfort within the proposed Prime University Senate Building, Abuja, using building performance simulation techniques. The study assesses the influence of design variables such as courtyard configuration, window placement, building orientation, facade treatments, and roof-level daylight openings on daylight distribution and visual comfort, while proposing strategies for improving building performance and reducing dependence on artificial lighting in institutional buildings.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews the concept of daylighting and user comfort, visual comfort theory, architectural strategies for daylight

enhancement, and the application of simulation tools in evaluating daylight performance within buildings.

2.1 Concept of Daylighting and User Comfort

Daylighting refers to the controlled admission of natural light into buildings to provide adequate illumination for indoor activities while minimizing reliance on artificial lighting (Tabadkani et al., 2021). Effective daylighting contributes to visual comfort, energy efficiency, and occupant well-being by creating pleasant and productive indoor environments. According to Htet et al. (2023), user comfort in daylighted spaces is influenced by factors such as illumination levels, daylight distribution, glare control, and access to outdoor views. In addition to providing sufficient illumination, user comfort involves visual satisfaction, reduced eye strain, and the ability of occupants to perform tasks efficiently within the indoor environment.

Similarly, studies have shown that well-designed daylighting systems enhance concentration, productivity, and occupant satisfaction while reducing energy consumption associated with artificial lighting (Vásquez et al., 2022). Access to natural daylight also promotes psychological well-being and improves the overall quality of indoor spaces (Landvreugd et al., 2025; Madan et al., 2024). Consequently, daylighting remains a critical design strategy for achieving user comfort and sustainability in contemporary buildings

2.2 Visual Comfort Theory

Visual Comfort Theory is a lighting and environmental design concept that explains the relationship between lighting conditions and occupants' ability to perform visual tasks comfortably, safely, and efficiently. The theory emphasizes that visual comfort is achieved when indoor lighting provides adequate illumination, balanced luminance distribution, minimal glare, and appropriate access to natural daylight (Mahgoub et al., 2025). It further suggests that well-designed lighting environments reduce visual fatigue, improve concentration, and enhance occupants' psychological well-being and productivity (Boyce, 2014; Mahgoub et al., 2025).

In architectural design, Visual Comfort Theory supports the integration of daylight-responsive strategies such as proper building orientation, optimized window placement and sizing, courtyards, light shelves, and external shading devices. These strategies help regulate daylight penetration, improve the uniformity of indoor illumination, and minimize excessive brightness contrasts that may cause discomfort glare. In educational and administrative buildings, visually comfortable environments are particularly important because they support sustained visual performance, occupant satisfaction, and energy-efficient building operation

Accordingly, Visual Comfort Theory provides the theoretical basis for evaluating how daylighting strategies influence user

comfort in the proposed Prime University Senate Building, Abuja. The theory underpins the study's assessment of daylight availability, glare control, and overall indoor visual quality through simulation-based analysis.

2.3 Architectural Strategies for Daylighting Enhancement

As posited by Aluko et al., (2022) the effectiveness of daylighting largely depends on architectural design decisions. Building orientation, window size and placement, glazing characteristics, and window-to-wall ratios influence the quantity and quality of daylight entering interior spaces. In addition, Ahmed et al., (2025) averred that courtyards, skylights, clerestory windows, and shading devices are widely used to improve daylight penetration and distribution, particularly in deep-plan buildings. While in tropical climates, integrating these strategies with climate-responsive facade treatments helps achieve adequate daylight levels while minimizing glare and excessive solar heat gain (Aslam et al., 2024; Onubogu et al., 2021).

2.4 Simulation-Based Daylighting Assessment and Research Gap

Advances in building performance simulation have enabled architects to evaluate daylight conditions and optimize design solutions before construction. As posited by Achoba et al., (2021) and Htet et al., (2023), simulation tools provide reliable assessments of daylight availability, visual comfort, and building performance using indicators such as Daylight Factor (DF), Spatial Daylight Autonomy (sDA),

and Annual Sunlight Exposure (ASE). Despite increasing interest in sustainable building design, simulation-based studies focusing on daylighting performance in university administrative buildings in Nigeria remain limited. Furthermore, little attention has been given to evaluating courtyard-based daylighting strategies within Abuja's tropical savannah climate. This study addresses this gap by assessing the daylight performance of the proposed Prime University Senate Building and examining the effectiveness of selected architectural daylighting strategies in enhancing user comfort.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

As posited by Uji (2009), research is an intensive activity that is based on the work of others and generates new ideas to pursue new questions and answers. This view is consistent with the assertion of Creswell and Creswell (2018) that research is a systematic process of inquiry designed to develop knowledge through the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data. This section describes study location and area, research design. Moreover, this part explains building description and daylighting design concept, and daylighting design variables.

3.1 Study Location and Area

Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) of Nigeria, is a planned city established in 1976 and designed by the renowned architect and urban planner Kenzo Tange (Ola-Adisa et al., 2015) (Figure 1). Located within the Guinea Savannah ecological zone, the city experiences

a tropical savannah climate characterized by distinct wet and dry seasons and high solar radiation levels throughout the year (Abubakar, 2014). These climatic conditions provide

significant potential for daylight-responsive design strategies that enhance visual comfort and reduce dependence on artificial lighting.

Figure 1: Abuja in National context

Source: Noma et al., (2022).

The proposed Prime University Senate Building, situated at Latitude 9.0563°N and Longitude 7.485°E, was used as the study location. While Abuja's climate is favourable for natural daylight utilization, effective design measures are required to minimize glare, excessive solar gains, and thermal discomfort.

3.2 Research Design

This study adopted a design-based research approach that combined literature review, architectural design exploration, and building performance simulation (Aslam et al., 2024; Zeng and Ou, 2025). The approach enabled the

evaluation of daylighting strategies during the design stage, allowing potential performance issues to be identified and addressed before construction.

3.3 Building Description and Daylighting Design Concept

The proposed Prime University Senate Building is a multi-storey administrative facility comprising executive offices, conference rooms, meeting spaces, and public service areas (Figure 2). The building was conceived using climate-responsive design principles, incorporating daylighting features such as a

central courtyard, optimized orientation, strategic fenestration, facade treatments, and roof-level openings to enhance daylight

penetration and occupant visual comfort (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Site layout and orientation of the proposed Prime University Senate Building, Abuja.

Source: Author's design, (2026).

The site plan illustrates the overall configuration and orientation of the proposed Prime University Senate Building within its immediate environment. The building was positioned to maximize access to natural daylight while maintaining functional circulation and adequate external spaces. The orientation strategy was informed by Abuja's

climatic conditions and high solar availability, enabling the building to harness daylight effectively while minimizing excessive solar exposure. The incorporation of an internal courtyard within the building mass further supports daylight penetration into deeper interior spaces (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Ground floor plan showing spatial organization and integrated daylighting features

Source: Author's design, (2026).

Figure 3 reveals the ground floor plan reveals showing spatial organization of the building and the integration of key daylighting elements. A central courtyard was incorporated as the primary daylighting device to improve the distribution of natural light to interior spaces located away from the external façade. Strategic placement of windows along the building perimeter enhances daylight penetration into offices, circulation areas, and public service spaces. The arrangement of functional spaces around the courtyard was intended to improve illumination uniformity and visual comfort throughout the building.

3.4 Daylighting Design Variables

Based on findings from previous daylighting studies (Aslam et al., 2024; Onubogu et al., 2021), the simulation assessed the influence of building orientation, courtyard configuration, window placement, facade treatments, and roof-level daylight openings on daylight distribution within the proposed Senate Building. These variables were selected because of their established role in improving daylight availability, illumination uniformity, and visual comfort in institutional buildings.

Figure 4: Section through the proposed Senate Building illustrating vertical daylighting strategies.

Source: Author's design, (2026).

The sectional view highlights the relationship between building form and daylight penetration across multiple floors. The central courtyard extends vertically through the building, allowing daylight to reach internal spaces on different levels (Figure 4). The section further illustrates the role of façade openings and roof-level daylight access in enhancing illumination within deeper floor plates. These architectural features were incorporated to improve daylight distribution, reduce reliance on artificial lighting, and enhance visual comfort across the building's occupied spaces.

4.0 DISCUSSIONS OF RESULTS

4.1 Daylighting Simulation Results

Daylighting performance of the proposed Prime University Senate Building was evaluated using

Sefaira under the climatic conditions of Abuja, Nigeria (Latitude 9.0563°N, Longitude 7.485°E). Daylight Factor (DF) was adopted as the primary performance indicator, where DF values below 2% indicate poor daylight availability, values between 2% and 5% indicate adequate daylighting, and values above 5% indicate very good daylight performance. The simulation results revealed variations in daylight distribution across the six floor levels of the building (Figure 5). Areas adjacent to external facades and courtyard openings consistently recorded higher daylight factor values, while deep-plan spaces, particularly the auditorium, exhibited lower daylight penetration.

Figure 5: Daylight factor distribution on the ground floor showing limited daylight penetration within the auditorium core and improved illumination around courtyard and perimeter spaces.

Source: Author's Sefaira Simulation (2026).

4.2 Comparative Daylighting Performance across Floors

The results in Table 1 indicate a progressive improvement in daylight availability from the

ground floor to the fifth floor. This trend is attributed to increased sky exposure, reduced external obstruction, and enhanced access to facade openings at higher levels.

Table 1: Summary of Daylight Performance across Building Floors

Floor Level	Typical DF Range (%)	Performance
Ground Floor	1–4	Moderate
First Floor	2–5	Good
Second Floor	3–6	Good
Third Floor	3–6	Good
Fourth Floor	3–6	Very Good
Fifth Floor	4–7	Very Good

Source: Author's construct, (2026).

Figure 6: Daylight factor distribution on the second floor showing improved daylight penetration within office wings and courtyard-adjacent spaces.

Source: Author's Sefaira Simulation (2026).

Figure 7: Daylight factor distribution on the third floor showing improved daylight penetration within office wings and courtyard-adjacent spaces.

Source: Author's Sefaira Simulation (2026).

Figure 8: Daylight factor distribution on the fourth floor showing improved daylight penetration within office wings and courtyard-adjacent spaces.

Source: Author's Sefaira Simulation (2026).

Figure 9: Fifth-floor daylight factor simulation indicating the highest daylight performance and enhanced daylight penetration resulting from increased sky exposure.

Source: Author's Sefaira Simulation (2026).

The fifth floor (Figure 9) demonstrated the highest daylight performance, while the ground

floor recorded the lowest daylight availability due to the depth of interior spaces and reduced sky visibility.

4.3 Influence of Design Variables on Daylighting Performance

The simulation findings demonstrate that daylight performance was strongly influenced by the selected daylighting strategies incorporated into the building design. The central courtyard proved to be the most effective daylighting element, significantly improving daylight penetration into adjacent offices and circulation spaces. Similarly, window placement, building orientation, and façade openings enhanced daylight distribution across occupied spaces. Vertical shading devices and roof overhangs helped regulate solar penetration while maintaining acceptable daylight levels. The improved daylight performance observed on the upper floors further highlights the positive impact of increased sky exposure on indoor visual conditions. Conversely, the auditorium consistently exhibited lower daylight factor values due to its deep-plan configuration and limited side openings, indicating the limitations of facade-based daylighting strategies in large-volume spaces.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

Three major findings emerged from the daylighting simulation of the proposed Prime University Senate Building.

First, the courtyard strategy significantly improved daylight penetration throughout the building. Spaces located adjacent to the

courtyard consistently recorded higher daylight factor values than interior spaces, confirming the effectiveness of architectural elements such as courtyards and atrium-like spaces in enhancing daylight distribution. This finding supports the observations of Bai et al., (2024) and Htet et al., (2023), who reported that appropriately designed daylighting features improve daylight penetration and visual comfort within deeper building spaces.

Second, daylight performance improved progressively with building height. Upper floors achieved higher daylight factor values due to increased sky exposure and reduced external obstruction. This finding is consistent with studies by Anumah et al., (2017) and Sinha (2020), which identified building orientation and access to natural light as important determinants of indoor daylight availability and environmental quality.

Third, the auditorium remained the weakest-performing space throughout the simulation. Although daylight conditions improved on the upper floors, the deep-plan geometry and limited façade openings restricted natural light penetration. This observation aligns with the findings of Tabadkani et al., (2021) and Aslam et al., (2024), who emphasized that effective daylight performance in large-volume spaces requires additional daylighting interventions and glare-control measures beyond conventional side-lighting approaches.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that passive daylighting strategies, including courtyard integration, appropriate fenestration design,

and building form optimization, can significantly enhance visual comfort and reduce dependence on artificial lighting. This outcome supports the conclusions of Gwaivangmin (2016), Gentile et al., (2022), and Muhammed et al., (2025), who reported that effective daylighting strategies improve building performance, occupant comfort, and energy efficiency in institutional environments.

4.5 Design Implications

Based on the simulation results, the study recommends the retention of the courtyard system as a primary daylighting strategy. Additional measures such as skylights, clerestory windows, and reflective interior finishes should be incorporated within the auditorium to improve daylight distribution. Furthermore, the use of shading devices and optimized glazing ratios should be maintained to balance daylight admission and solar heat control.

5.0 CONCLUSION OF FINDINGS

The daylighting simulation confirms that the integration of courtyards, facade openings, and passive daylighting strategies can significantly

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improve visual comfort and reduce dependence on artificial lighting within university administrative buildings. However, additional roof-level daylighting interventions are required to enhance daylight performance in deep-plan spaces such as the auditorium.

6.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The courtyard design strategy should be maintained and enhanced in the proposed Senate Building, as it significantly improved daylight penetration and visual comfort in adjacent spaces.
2. Daylighting simulation tools should be integrated into the early design stages of institutional buildings to evaluate and optimize daylight performance before construction.
3. Future studies should investigate additional daylighting performance metrics, such as Spatial Daylight Autonomy (sDA), Annual Sunlight Exposure (ASE), and post-occupancy evaluations, to provide a more comprehensive assessment of visual comfort and building performance.

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